

Rajyoga Lifestyle, Biological Clock, and Spiritual Happiness among Educated Youth: A Study of Brahma Kumaris

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Abstract:

The materialistic and human-denying scientific worldviews of today have played a major role in the development of science and its flourishing material benefits. But too much attachment to physical consciousness and material pursuits has been linked with an increase in stress, anxiety, mental fatigue and emotional instability among educated youth. With the advancement of science and technology, the young people today have more comfort and convenience than ever before, however, more and more young people are plagued by economic pressure, social entanglements, family conflicts, psychological problems, etc. which have a negative impact on their lives and even lead to suicidal attitudes. This has created a concern for the educated youth about finding happiness, peace, mental stability and meaningful life. The teachings of the Brahma Kumaris, a global spiritual movement founded in India in 1936, provide a detailed blueprint for spiritual health and well-being, employing Raja Yoga meditation, self-awareness, positive thinking, managing emotions, mindfulness and teaching spiritual values. The teachings seek to foster inner peace, moral behavior, harmonious relationships, and the individual's overall growth. This study looks into the correlation of Brahma Kumaris teachings with producing spiritual happiness in educated youth and its effect on mental, physical, familial and social well-

being. The study uses both qualitative and quantitative research approaches to examine the impact that these teachings have on participants' levels of spiritual happiness, life satisfaction, emotional wellbeing and inner peace. The results show that educated youth who interacted with the teachings experienced a high level of spiritual happiness, joy and peace. Additionally, there was an evident reduction in indicators related to stress, anxiety and psychological distress, reflecting an overall improvement of quality of life. The result of this study is that the education imparted by Brahma Kumaris is an effective spiritual program that can be used to bring happiness, psychological well being and holistic development in the midst of educated youth.

Keywords: Brahma Kumaris, Raja Yoga Meditation, Spiritual Happiness, Educated Youth, Inner Peace, Self-Awareness, Positive Thinking, Emotional Well-Being, Personal Growth, Life Satisfaction.

1. Introduction

Today's youth are rapidly progressing in education, technology, and career advancements, yet the problems of mental stress, depression, and dissatisfaction are constantly increasing. A lack of inner peace and contentment is emerging as a major cause of this imbalance.

At such times, spirituality emerges as a powerful medium that can provide the experience of inner peace and joy.

The Brahma Kumaris, which offers teachings based on Raja Yoga and self-knowledge, inspires youth toward self-reflection and positive thinking. The organization aims to foster awareness of spiritual purity, morality, and life values. The teachings of the Brahma Kumaris influence young people not only from a religious perspective, but also from a scientific and psychological perspective. Educated young people have greater awareness and logical thinking, which makes them want to understand spirituality not just through faith, but also through experience and analysis. Rajyoga meditation develops mental peace, self-confidence, and a balanced outlook on life. This research will analyze the impact of Brahma Kumari teachings on educated youth and their level of spiritual bliss. Spiritual bliss is an inner experience that provides a person with satisfaction and peace beyond external circumstances.